

Deep learning-based supraglacial lake extent and depth detection on the Greenland Ice Sheet by combining ICESat-2 and Sentinel-2 data

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Supraglacial lakes are an important parameter for understanding the current and future state of the Greenland Ice Sheet. Previous studies have focused on mapping supraglacial lake extent using optical and radar imagery, while lake depth is more difficult to estimate due to sparse temporal and spatial coverage of laser altimeters such as ICESat-2. We present a supervised deep learning approach to predict lake extent and depth based on the subtle spectral signatures acquired from Sentinel-2 imagery. The model is trained on an existing lake extent product and elevation profiles derived from ICESat-2. The output of this approach is a proof-of-concept study whereby deep learning can utilise contextual information from the input image to produce a lake depth and extent prediction. The preliminary results show that the methodology is feasible as the output model successfully produces a reasonable lake extent and depth prediction despite data limitations. This work forms part of the European Space Agency’s Greenland Ice Sheet Climate Change Initiative (ESA GIS CCI+), which runs from December 2022 until 2025.

Abbreviations

Arctic Science Integration Quest (ASIAQ), Deep Learning (DL), False Negative (FN), False Positive (FP), Greenland Ice Sheet (GrIS), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI), Supraglacial Lakes (SGL), Surface Mass Balance (SMB), True Negative (TN), Top of Atmosphere (TOA), True Positive (TP)

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

In the last three decades, the Greenland Ice Sheet (GrIS) has lost ~4000 gigatonnes of ice, resulting in ~11mm of

sea level rise [1]. The main contributors are the north-west, south-east and central west sectors [2]. The mass loss regime on GrIS is bimodal, with roughly equal contributions from surface mass balance (SMB) and glacier dynamical imbalance [1]. The latter describes discharge due to increased ice velocity and iceberg calving, while SMB is the difference between precipitation, sublimation, and meltwater runoff [1]. In the last 20 years, the influence that SMB (including supraglacial lakes) has on mass loss has increased, highlighting the need for better observational coverage [2].

Supraglacial lakes (hereafter SGLs) are temporary reservoirs of water that interact to form highly complex and dynamic hydrological networks [3]. They form from the accumulation of meltwater on the surface of the ice sheet during the melt season (May to October). SGLs drain either laterally across the ice surface, forming streams and networks which eventually drain into the ocean [4], or vertically through the ice sheet via moulins. Determining the type of drainage regime is important, as moulins transport water from the surface to the subglacial bed [5]. In regions lacking efficient drainage networks, vertical water transfer can act to lubricate the ice which increases ice flow speed [3]. Finally, SGLs store latent heat on the surface of the ice sheet, which affects surface heat fluxes [6]. To quantify the impact of meltwater on the GrIS, widespread observations of total SGL volume (i.e extent and depth) is required [7].

1.2. Lake extent observations

SGL extent on the periphery of the GrIS has been mapped extensively using remote sensing techniques, with the majority of research focusing on areas of interest such as NE and SW Greenland [8, 9]. Previous studies [10–12] have mapped SGL extent using red band reflectance from MODIS imagery using semi or fully automatic methods, while others [13–15] have utilised ratios between blue and red visible bands from Sentinel-2 imagery and Landsat 7/8. Machine and deep learning solutions to map lake area have shown to be promising [16–18].

1.3. Lake depth observations

While there are optical methods to estimate SGL depth from spectral-based methods such as Landsat 7/8, WorldView and MODIS imagery [3, 19, 20], other more precise methods such as laser altimetry from IceSat-2 [21] only have partial coverage of the ice sheet due to the along-track laser altimeter and relatively long repeat pass time of 91 days [22]. Previous projects such as 4DGreenland, upon which this study is built, produced a hydrology assessment of the GrIS using remote sensing methods. Here SGL depth retrievals from optical imagery and IceSat-2 altimetry data were compared [23] but no catchment-wide product was produced. Additionally, the lack of in-situ measurements means that widespread remote sensing and ground truth data of lake bathymetry (and consequently lake volume) do not exist for the GrIS.

1.4. Deep learning

Deep learning (DL) algorithms form a subset of machine learning techniques, which are methods used within Artificial Intelligence (AI). In supervised DL, the algorithm ‘learns’ which features are important for classification by back-propagating the error between an input image and its’ label [24]. DL techniques have been utilised for image classification for a range of applications, such as medical and satellite imagery [25].

U-Nets are specific DL architectures that were originally developed for medical imagery applications [26, 27], but have since shown high levels of success for a range of image segmentation problems [28]. The skip connections between each convolutional step of the encoder and its’ corresponding decoder allow contextual information to be considered before making a prediction [29]. For SGLs, contextual information such as floating ice, sediment, and shadows complicate spectral signatures from optical imagery, potentially leading to inaccurate depth estimations. Therefore, a trained U-Net has the potential to outperform aforementioned physics-based approaches by making use of context to create a realistic estimation of lake depth.

1.5. Research aims

Approximating the measurements of IceSat-2 data from Sentinel-2 optical imagery carries the potential to provide dense spatial and temporal meltwater volume calculations. Due to the complexity of the task and the recent success of DL models for image processing, we use a joint classification and regression model in an attempt to fulfill data and knowledge gaps. Although similar research has been able to constrain SGL depth estimates from satellite imagery using IceSat-2 [30], to the best of our knowledge, DL has not yet been exploited to predict SGL depth from Sentinel-2. Here, we present preliminary results which explore the feasibility of using DL for SGL observations in NE Greenland.

2. Data

2.1. Study area

Located in NE Greenland (Fig. 1), Nioghalvfjærdsbræ and Zachariae Isstrøm (hereafter 79°N and Zachariae, respectively) drain ~12% of the entire continent [31, 32].

In recent years, 79°N has experienced a net loss of ice due to acceleration of flow, while Zachariae’s floating ice tongue collapsed in 2012 [13]. While previously it was believed that NE Greenland was not susceptible to ocean and atmospheric warming, it is now thought that both glaciers are being strongly affected by climate change [13]. As such, the NE sector is recognised as having great importance on the overall stability of the GrIS, due to the large discharge potential caused by de-buttressing post ice shelf collapse [2]. Whilst the seasonal evolution and spatial distribution of SGLs in NE Greenland is understudied [31], it is known that the region experiences the largest amount of SGLs in Greenland due to its’ relatively gentle sloping terrain [16]. Here, we take the 2019 summer melt season (May to October) over 79°N and Zachariae glaciers as our study period.

2.2. Data collection

Sentinel-2 data

The input images are from Sentinel-2 Level-1C product. The 110x110 km² tiles have radiometric measurements that are adjusted for Top Of Atmosphere (TOA) reflectances. Images were selected based on a threshold of <10% cloud cover and were visually inspected to ensure the presence of visible lakes. The 10m resolution bands (B02, B03, B04, and B08) formed the four input channels for the network. In total, the model was trained using 9 partially labeled Sentinel-2 scenes from 20th June to 26th August, 2019 and validated with 3 scenes with lake extent labels from the 14th June to 20th August and 5 scenes with lake depth labels from 17th July to 22nd August.

Lake extent labels

Currently, we use an existing SGL extent data product generated by a previous CCI project [35]. The product was generated using an automated thresholding technique (Normalised Difference Water Index; NDWI), which is derived from Sentinel-2 data for the 79°N and Zachariae glaciers during the 2019 melt season.

Basic pre-processing was performed, such as the removal of large areas of slush. The labels were given a background class which includes any ice, slush, and rock present in the corresponding Sentinel-2 image. No manual editing or enhancement of extent labels was performed.

Fig. 1 Map of the study area, located in NE Greenland (Generated using QGreenland [33]). Blue drainage delineations are based on the ‘Zwally Greenland Drainage Basins’ [34].

Lake depth labels

SGL depth for the 2019 melt season was derived from along-track laser altimeter measurements from the ATLAS instrument onboard the IceSat-2 satellite [36]. The product used, ATL03, contains geolocated photon heights measured above the WGS 84 ellipsoid. Photons emitted by the instrument are received by the satellite, including background photons. The low-level processing allows the retrieved photons to provide information about the SGL surface and bathymetry.

IceSat-2 tracks that intersected with the extent labels were processed to produce a point-based lake depth estimation as a cross-section of the lake [37]. Bathymetry data from the strong and weak beams were rasterised as point cloud datasets separately.

Training/validation data split

We split the extent and depth labels based on the temporal and spatial extent of the Sentinel-2 images. Both labels were filtered to within ± 1 days of the image acquisition date and clipped to the extent of the Sentinel-2 image. In total, the model was trained using 6 Sentinel-2 scenes from 20th June to 26th August and validated with 3 scenes from the 14th June to 20th August. It should be noted that we did not create a test split as testing will be carried out independently by ASIAQ later in the project.

3. Methods

The main model and training parameters are summarised in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. We use a standard 4-block U-Net model with an input shape of $4 \times 512 \times 512$ and an output shape of $3 \times 512 \times 512$, with two channels for binary classification (background/lake in one hot encoding) and one for regression (lake depth). Preprocessing and augmentation of the data (see 3.2) are performed on slightly larger ($768 \times 768 \text{px}$) image chips in order to avoid preprocessing-related artifacts.

Due to the size of the Sentinel-2 imagery, the data must be split up into $512 \times 512 \text{px}$ chips with an overlapping sliding window. To avoid edge artifacts in the model during training and inference, only a slightly smaller region of the image is used: centred $480 \times 480 \text{px}$ for loss calculations, and $432 \times 432 \text{px}$ for inference. Discarding the edge pixels ensures that a large enough spatial context is considered for each segmented pixel.

We optimise the model using Dice Loss [38] for predicting SGL extent (classification) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for predicting SGL depth (regression) from the strong and weak labels. Weighting ratios are applied so that the Dice Loss and MAE are balanced.

3.1. Evaluation metrics

Since the background class (e.g. ice and rock) are over 100x more frequent than the predicted foreground class, there is a significant class imbalance. Dice Loss has an inherent class balancing property, and it is a differentiable proxy loss for optimizing F1-Score (also known as Dice coefficient) as it is one of the most frequently used metrics for class imbalance problems [39] and ensures comparability with other studies. In addition to F1-Score, we calculate secondary metrics for SGL extent (True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives, False Negatives, and Overall Accuracy). For SGL depth, we record MAE and Mean Squared Error (MSE) as secondary metrics. We apply validation based early stopping to avoid overfitting.

Table 1 Summary of model parameters

Model parameter	Value
Deep learning model	U-Net
Number of levels	4
Input shape	$4 \times 512 \times 512$
Output shape	$3 \times 512 \times 512$
Padding	replication
Batch size	16
Kernel size	3
Initial filters	16
Upsampling	bilinear
Activation	LeakyReLU
Normalization	batch

Table 2 Summary of training parameters

Training parameter	Value
Epochs	100
Dice Loss weight	1×10^{-3}
MAE loss weight (weak:strong)	1:2
Learning rate	1×10^{-3}

3.2. Augmentations

In order to prevent overfit, we employ the following augmentations on the training images, extent and depth labels: crop, rotate, flip, scale, roll (rolling an image around) and cow mix batch (taking two images from different batches and overlaying them; [40]). All augmentations were enabled with a probability of $p=0.3$, and no augmentations were applied to the validation images. It should be noted that only spatial augmentations were applied based on

the assumption that significant colour distortions may negatively affect SGL depth prediction.

4. Results

Table 3 Model validation results for primary (F1-Score and MAE) and secondary metrics (TP, TN, FP, FN, OA, MSE, SD).

Metric	Task	Value
F1-score	cls	0.48
MAE	reg	1.03 m
True Positive (TP)	cls	867813 px
True Negative (TN)	cls	340260035 px
False Positive (FP)	cls	60351 px
False Negative (FN)	cls	1826457 px
Overall Accuracy (OA)	cls	0.99
MSE	reg	2.08 m
SD	reg	1.44 m

During the validation loop, the F1-Score reached a maximum of 0.48 (Table 3). The correctly predicted lake and background classes (340260035 and 867813, respectively) dominated over the number of Type 1 (FP) and 2 (FN) errors (60351 and 1826457, respectively).

At its' best performance, the model returned a MAE value of 1.03m. The secondary evaluation metrics for regression, SD and MSE, achieved results of 1.44m and 2.08m, respectively.

A sample of a set of predictions in the validation loop is shown in Fig. 3.

5. Discussion

5.1. Model performance

The aim of this study was to test the feasibility of using Sentinel-2 data to jointly predict SGL extent and depth with DL. It is evident in Fig. 3 that the model can be trained on ground truth labels to produce a model which creates a prediction for both SGL extent and depth from only Sentinel-2 imagery. It must be noted that in this case, optimisation was not the end goal, and both the model and data will be optimised for better performance in future work throughout the two-year project.

The final model will be cross-validated by an independent group on data that was not used during model development.

Fig. 2 Density scatter plot and frequency density (top and right) for SGL depth predictions from the model versus the SGL ground truth label. Blue indicates low frequency and green indicates high frequency of data points.

5.2. SGL extent

Fig. 3b shows that the foreground class (lake) was well predicted in many cases, while the background class was predicted with ease and precision across all months. Lake predictions were more precise when isolated, large, and round lakes were present in the images. Conversely, lakes that had not fully developed yet and in areas with large amounts of slush performed worse (Fig. 4b). Typically, lake edges produced the highest error (Fig. 3c), highlighting the difficulty in providing a high-probability prediction in cases where the pixel could either be lake or ice. For very dark, deep lakes, the model was not able to classify correctly (Fig. 4d). One reason for this could be that the dark ice surrounding deeper lakes led to uncertainty during classification, as in most other cases the lakes are surrounded by 'clean' ice. Finally, highly crevassed regions such as on the surface of 79°N glacier performed worse compared to the smoother terrain further inland (Fig. 4f).

As mentioned, the Dice Loss has an inherent class balancing property but the extreme class imbalance and label noise still pose an important challenge. Given the extreme class imbalance, a noise-robust loss can easily incorrectly consider a large portion of pixels as FP or FN. While the feasibility of the method was not affected by these challenges, they have to be considered during performance optimization.

While our work does not currently surpass the performance of previous work aimed at predicting SGL extent

Fig. 3 Top left(a): Sentinel-2 RGB sample, top right(b): SGL extent prediction where blue is lake and grey is background, bottom left(c): SGL extent prediction error where green denotes correct prediction and pink is incorrect, bottom right(d): SGL depth prediction.

from satellite imagery [17, 18], it does show how a range of DL (Attention Based U-Net) and ML (Convolutional Neural Networks) methods can be used to create high performing image segmentation models. Prior and ongoing research also showcases how DL methods can exploit many data sources (Such as Landsat 8) to produce SGL extent maps. The main benefit of the DL approach is that it can be easily adjusted to other sensors only by providing learning data and without the need for sensor-specific research and design.

Fig. 4 Prediction challenges presented for the current U-Net model caused by SGL variability (slush, deep lakes and crevasses). The left column shows the Sentinel-2 RGB samples while the right show the corresponding extent prediction where green pixels are correct prediction and pink pixels are incorrect predictions.

5.3. SGL depth

Despite the sparsity of SGL depth labels, the model was able to make use of Sentinel-2 images to produce some reasonable predictions of SGL depth, even when the depth labels were not available. Similarly to the ex-

tent predictions, the algorithm worked best with isolated, easily distinguishable lakes. In such cases, lakes were predicted to be deeper in the middle of lakes compared to the periphery (Fig. 3d). As shown in Fig. 2, the model successfully predicted lakes with depths between 0-2m with a SD of 1.44m, while lakes deeper than 3m proved more problematic. There are likely several reasons behind this behaviour. First, the multitask optimization virtually never achieves the optimum for the two tasks at the same moment. Optimizing only for lake depth probably would yield better performance. Second, the deep lakes have noisier labels due to the lower signal-to-noise ratio in the IceSat-2 measurements for deep lakes. Third, the deep lake pixels are relatively infrequent. MAE has better properties to ignore outlier values [41, 42], which is beneficial for noise, but a drawback for deep lakes as they get less contribution than other losses would provide such as MSE. Finally, the optimization loss choice depends on the application of the final results, e.g. optimizing for minimal volumetric error or optimizing for lake topography would lead to different choices. For instance, boundary losses are popular for instance and object segmentation tasks but they assume relatively noise-free labels and they optimize for edges, not for the whole volume. Downstream users should consider how much the above choices might affect the results, and if these tradeoffs are compatible with their requirements.

To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies predicting SGL depth using DL, although there have been similar applications mapping river flood depth and extent [43, 44]. It is evident that adapting classic DL architectures like U-Net to optimise for a specific application can produce specialised architectures and better results. This could be useful for future experiments where the multitask network could be tweaked for the optimisation for SGL depth, given that SGL extent predictions generally performed better.

5.4. Limitations

Data quality

The quality of training data is undeniably the most important part of achieving high-quality models. While the Sentinel-2 images were assumed to be “cloud-free” due to the filtering step during data collection, <10% cloud cover does not guarantee cloud-free conditions which can lead to the model misclassifying cloud. Thus, future work may demand more stringent filtering and/or cloud masking.

The quality of both the extent and depth labels is also imperfect. The extent shapefiles include large swaths of surface water (slush or shallow melt) and there are many cases of mismatch between the label and the corresponding Sentinel-2 image. Despite manual filtering for individual, realistic lakes with as little timewise mismatch as possible, there were still lakes in the Sentinel-2 scenes

that did not have a corresponding label, which negatively affects training. To minimise the potential issues caused by data quality, SGL extent labels will need filtering using a reasonable minimum lake size, as well as manual enhancement/adjustment.

Data coverage

Although our results prove promising for the input data given, it is unlikely that all aforementioned variability of SGLs and optical imagery is captured. In this work, data limitations led to a restricted temporal and spatial coverage of input data. For instance, only using labels and images from NE Greenland in 2019 will create a model which works well for specific conditions (crevassed, low sloping regions) but is not generalisable to other regions. Similarly, years with more or less meltwater relative to 2019 are likely to lead to poorer predictions. While augmentations were used to reduce this effect, the model would have been more generalisable if more data was available.

Assumptions

It is assumed that all lakes are 'clean' (with little bottom debris). This is likely an overly-simplistic assumption since debris and sediment are common on the surface of the ice sheet and can accumulate in a lake [21]. 'Dirty' lakes make it challenging for the IceSat-2 product to retrieve reliable information since the backscattering properties are altered, leading to noisy SGL depth predictions. Identifying clean and dirty lakes in future work will improve our understanding of how depth predictions are made.

Similarly, the clear sky measurement condition assumes that the atmospheric effects are minimal and can be learned by the model. While DL models are robust estimators, additional context and incorporation of physical models could improve the performance, ie. incorporating all Sentinel-2 band data and potentially using Level-2 bottom-of-atmosphere / surface reflectance images. However, relying on such physical models would make the approach harder to generalize to other sensors.

5.5. Future work

Improved input data

In future work, we propose to exploit all Sentinel-2 bands to test whether the unique spectral signatures of other wavelengths can improve the detection of SGL extent and depth. In addition, the research will focus on increasing the spatial and temporal range of SGL extent and depth prediction; first to different years in NE Greenland and second to other regions such as SW Greenland and Antarctica. A generalised model has the potential to predict SGL depth prior to the launch of IceSat-2, which would

serve as a significant tool for improving past observations of the GrIS.

Model optimisation

Implementing pre-training as a form of transfer learning could lead to quicker convergence and better model performance [45]. Later experimentation will also include hyperparameter optimisation in order to automatically find the best hyperparameter combinations [46]. Additionally, adapted U-Net architectures, either previously published or new, may help the algorithm to extract more abstract and useful features from the Sentinel-2 imagery.

In addition to the improved data, semi-supervised learning could be explored for utilizing the vast amount of unlabeled data. We consider the consistency training technique [47], where unlabeled images and their augmented counterpart are used for prediction, and loss penalty is applied if the predictions are different.

Finally, it is evident that augmentations helped increase sample sizes and prevent overfit without hindering the model's ability to make a prediction. Accordingly, extending the use of other augmentations, such as Gaussian noise, may help to further increase robustness. Introducing dropout in future testing may also improve the generalisability of the model [48].

Improved functionality

Creating multi-class labels to include slush, rock, and cloud could be explored as additional functionality of the algorithm, rather than a two-class classification problem. Later experimentation may involve using data from other optical sensors such as Landsat 8/9, or even different types of remote sensing techniques such as SAR from Sentinel-1 or radar altimetry from CryoSat-2.

6. Conclusion

Given that SGLs are an active and important parameter on the GrIS, scientific efforts should be focused on improving meltwater volume calculations. DL has shown to be successful in its prediction of SGL extent, while SGL depth is more complex and comparatively understudied. Here we present a novel method using a multi-task U-Net to predict SGL extent and depth from Sentinel-2 imagery using relatively sparse ground truth labels. From our preliminary experimentation, it is evident that the proposed methodology is feasible. Whilst isolated, large, and round lakes were well predicted, other instances such as slush, crevasses, lake edges, deep lakes, and cloud coverage all presented challenges for the algorithm. SGL depth performed best in cases with shallow lakes (0-2m) while having more difficulty with shallower and deeper lakes. As expected, SGL extent showed more success compared to SGL depth

which is likely due to the amount of ground-truth labels and model optimisation favoured towards SGL extent. We believe that with extra work on label quality and quantity, many of the outstanding challenges mentioned above could be addressed.

This work is the output of the first six months of a two-year project, whereby future work will include model optimisation, further augmentations, better data coverage, extended functionality, and independent validation.

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Author contributions

A. E. Robinson performed the analyses, wrote the paper, and produced the figures. D. Völgyes and M. Vermeer edited the paper and assisted in analyses, data interpretation, and discussion of results. D. S. M. Fantin oversaw and managed the project. L. S. Sørensen and M. Aa. Kruse performed the analysis and produced the dataset comprising the IceSat-2 depth labels. S. Frosch developed the algorithm for deriving lake bathymetry from IceSat-2 data.

Disclosure

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